

ISic3131

I.Sicily inscription 3131

Language

Ancient Greek

Type**Material**

limestone

Object

statue

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Private collection

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI330186

1. ΥΠΑΚ.

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645472

PHI 330186

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 28.0762

Rizza, G. 1976-1977. Attività dell'Istituto di Archeologia dell'Università di Catania (Scavi e ricerche in Sicilia negli anni 1972-1975). *Kokalos*. 22-23: 636-646. At 640 tav.CXXXIX

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